

Risk Stratification for Cardiotoxicity in Breast Cancer Patients: Predicting Early Decline of LVEF After Treatment*

Kostas M. Tsiouris, Alexandros Mitsis, Grigoris Grigoriadis, Georgia Karanasiou, Lampros Lakkas, Davide Mauri, Maria Angeliki Toli, Alexia Alexandraki, Kalliopi Keramida, Daniela Cardinale and Dimitrios I. Fotiadis, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract— This study introduces AI-based models in prediction and risk assessment of early cardiac dysfunction in older breast cancer patients, as a side-effect of their cancer treatment. Using only features extracted during the baseline evaluation of each patient the proposed methodology could predict a decline in LVEF values in 4 different follow-up intervals during the first year after treatment initiation (i.e. months 3-12), with a mean accuracy of 66.67% and up to 73.55%. Selected baseline predictive factors were ranked according to their prevalence in the evaluation experiments, replicating the importance of various cardiac disorders at baseline, LVEF value and a higher age, which are all previously reported, while introducing Diabetes as an important risk factor.

Clinical Relevance— Healthcare providers can better assess cardiovascular health status and risk of cardiotoxicity in the cancer treatment continuum. This will enable timely intervention and close monitoring on high risk patients while saving resources for low risk patients.

I. INTRODUCTION

More than 50% of the newly diagnosed breast cancer patients are older than 65 years of age and are particularly susceptible to the cardiotoxic effects of cancer treatment due to age-related risk factors, pre-existing heart disease and a high prevalence of multiple co-morbidities [1]. If the multi-morbidity aspect of breast cancer patient management is not carefully controlled during cancer treatment, there is an increased risk of providing fragmented and poorly coordinated healthcare. This becomes particularly important since an unnoticed high risk of cardiotoxicity in this vulnerable group of patients may lead to inappropriate interventions and undertreatment of cardiac implications, resulting in poorer treatment response and morbidity outcomes, deterioration of quality of life and increased healthcare costs [2].

The current standard of cardiac monitoring after cancer treatment is based on repeated echocardiography evaluations of the left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF). A decline in LVEF values can reliably declare that functional cardiac

impairment has occurred. In a recent landmark study, a large cancer patient population (i.e. 2,625 subjects in total, 51% breast cancer patients) showed that monitoring of LVEF after the end of chemotherapy enabled almost all cases of cardiotoxicity to be identified during the first 12 months of follow-up [3]. The study also showed that timely treatment with ACE inhibitors and beta-blockers, allowed 82% of the patients to normalize their heart function. However, only 11% of these patients showed a full recovery (i.e. same LVEF value as before chemotherapy), as the majority of patients, although significantly improved due to following cardio-protective treatment, failed to reach their baseline LVEF value. These findings confirmed that assessing and timely identifying the risk of cardiotoxicity, or even better predicting a later functional decrease at baseline, when there is still a greater potential for reversing this course, could enable physicians to deploy such counter measures in time, before a critical extent of myocardial damage has occurred and compensation mechanisms have been exhausted [4-5].

Improving prediction of cardiovascular risks on (breast) cancer patients has remained for long an unmet clinical need [6]. In a recent study, data from 787 breast cancer patients were analyzed showing that a lower baseline LVEF value is prognostic of treatment-related cardiac dysfunction (63% [59–66] vs. 65% [61–68], $p=0.016$), with a 5% or more decline in LVEF within month 3 after chemotherapy being strongly associated with higher cardiotoxicity risk ($p<0.001$) [7]. Upshaw *et al.*, proposed a multivariate statistical model to identify factors associated with higher risk of cardiotoxicity in breast cancer patients (i.e. 967 women, 51 developed cardiotoxicity), adding older age, higher Body Mass Index (BMI), besides lower baseline LVEF at baseline as valuable prognostic factors [8]. The results from a similar retrospective study based on 212 women diagnosed with breast cancer (72 patients with LVEF declined 10% or more during follow-up), confirmed the predictive values of age, BMI and LVEF values, while adding systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mitral peak E-wave velocity and left ventricular end-systolic diameter [9].

*Research supported by CARDIOCARE project which is funded within the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (GA no. 945175) and PRECIOUS project, co-financed by Greece and the European Union—European Regional Development Fund under the Operational Program “Competitiveness Entrepreneurship Innovation” (EPAnEK), NSRF 2014-2020 (Project code: 82863, MIS: 5047133).

K.M. Tsiouris, A. Mitsis, G. Grigoriadis, G. Karanasiou, D.I. Fotiadis are with the Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Greece.

L. Lakkas is with the 2nd Cardiology Department, University Hospital of Ioannina, Greece.

D. Mauri is with the Dept. of Medical Oncology, University Hospital of Ioannina, Greece.

M. A. Toli is with the Dept. for Breast Cancer, Endocrine Tumors and Sarcoma, Karolinska University Hospital and the Dept. of Oncology-Pathology, Karolinska Institute.

A. Alexandraki is with the A.G. Leventis Clinical Trials Unit, Bank of Cyprus Oncology Centre, Nicosia, Cyprus.

K. Keramida is with the Dept. of Cardiology, Attikon University Hospital, Athens, Greece.

D. Cardinale is with the Cardioncology Unit, European Institute of Oncology IEO, IRCCS, Milan Italy.

K. M. Tsiouris, G. Karanasiou and D. I. Fotiadis are with the Biomedical Research Institute, FORTH, Ioannina, Greece (corresponding author's phone: +302651009006; email: fotiadis@uoi.gr).

This study aims to develop a risk prediction model able to risk stratify older breast cancer patients (≥ 55 years) for cardiac dysfunction, by evaluating a panel of diverse baseline factors using risk modelling tools based on machine learning. To the best of our knowledge this is the first time that a multi-center dataset is analyzed with AI techniques, in an attempt to develop a multiscale risk stratification and prediction model for the identification of patients with higher risk of developing cardiac dysfunction in 4 discrete time points within the first year after treatment initiation (i.e. Months 3, 6, 9 & 12). This will provide insights on the underline associations and interactions between clinical and biological factors with cardiotoxicity. The first version of this methodology will assess baseline risk factors, prognostic of early breast cancer treatment-induced cardiac dysfunction, as noted by a drop in follow-up LVEF values. This could eventually allow higher risk patients to be more closely monitored and receive cardio-protective treatment to preserve their baseline LVEF, contributing to more personalized management plans.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Study Protocol – Data description

One of the largest multi-center datasets is collected during the lifecycle of the CARDIOCARE project, consisting of 1,560 breast cancer patients treated with chemotherapy in 5 clinical centers across 4 countries: European Institute of Oncology (IEO), Bank of Cyprus Oncology Centre (BOCOC), Karolinska University Hospital (KSBC), National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) and University of Ioannina (UOI). Patient data are extracted retrospectively from existing health records, following Ethics Committees approval in line with the national requirements. The records contain multi-modal data with baseline and follow-up evaluations at different time points of patients’ treatment; as often as every 3 months and up to 12 months according to each site’s protocol.

In order to be included, patients (males/females) needed to fulfill the following inclusion criteria:

- Early breast cancer, with neoadjuvant and/or adjuvant treatment with regimens including anthracyclines.
- HER2 positive early breast cancer, with neoadjuvant and/or adjuvant treatment with anti-HER2 therapy.
- HER2 positive metastatic breast cancer, with first line therapy with anti-HER2 agents.
- Received first-line therapy in the metastatic setting with any type of treatment.
- Aged ≥ 65 years, with/without baseline cardiovascular or metabolic disease (any) before starting any active treatment for breast cancer.

TABLE I. CARDIOCARE MULTI-CENTER RETROSPECTIVE DATASET.

Country	Clinical center	Baseline & Follow-up data types collected	No. of patients
Italy	IEO	Cardiac imaging reports, Breast imaging, Blood tests, Biomarkers, QoL.	300
Cyprus	BOCOC	Cardiac imaging reports, Breast imaging, Blood tests, QoL.	600
Sweden	KSBC	Cardiac imaging reports, Breast imaging, Blood tests, Biomarkers, QoL.	260
Greece	UOI	Cardiac imaging reports, Breast imaging, Blood tests.	100
Greece	NKUA	Cardiac imaging reports, Breast imaging, Blood tests.	300
Total:			1,560

TABLE II. COMPLETE LIST OF BASELINE FEATURES TO BE USED AS PREDICTIVE FACTORS FOR LVEF DECLINE PER FOLLOW-UP INTERVAL.

Data source	Baseline Parameters – Features	Datatype
Clinical evaluation	Body Mass Index (BMI), Body Surface Area (BSA), Gender, Age (at time of therapy)	Continuous, Categorical
Medical history	Hypertension, Diabetes, Hyperlipidemia, Smoking, Chronic Kidney Disease, Cardiomyopathy, Severe Vascular Disease, Coronary Artery Disease, Congenital Heart Disease, Arrhythmia, Other Tumor	Categorical
CARDIO-ECHO reports	IVSd, PWd, LVIDd, iLV_Mass, iEDV, LVEF, GLS, BasalRV, FUN_S, SystRVPress, TAPSE, LAVI, E, A, E/A Ratio, DecelTime, E', Heart Rate, LBBB, RBBB, LAH, STAbnormal, QTc	Continuous, Categorical
Blood exams	White Blood Count (WBC), Neutrophils, Hemoglobin, Hematocrit, Platelets, Glucose, Creatinine, Albumin, SGOT_AST, SGPT, ALT, Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase (γ -GT), Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), CA, Na, K, Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH), Total Bilirubin	Continuous

- Aged ≥ 55 years, with/without cardiovascular risk factors before starting any active treatment for breast cancer.

Patients were excluded if their blood troponin levels were measured higher than the suggested upper values of the normally expected range for troponin values before chemotherapy. As shown in Table I, collected data include: i) cardiac structural and functional data by echocardiography and ECG, ii) biochemical biomarker data (e.g. troponin, NT-proBNP), iii) clinical data with medical records, demographics, medication, hospital admissions, iv) lab results from blood exams, v) health-related QoL assessments.

B. Harmonization - Pre-formatting

The first step was to harmonize all data records from the different clinical centers into a single dataset that can be used for predictive analytics. Very common issues when combining data entries from multi-center electronic health records, are the differences in naming schemes for the given set of clinical measurements (e.g. ‘Na’ or ‘Sodium’, ‘Platelets’ or ‘PLT’, etc.), and reporting of values for the same parameters in different units (e.g. ‘cm’ and ‘mm’, ‘UI/L’ and ‘UI/dL’, particle counts as ‘ 10^3 ’ and ‘ 10^6 ’, etc.). The harmonization step includes the identification of common primary parameters and the transformation of all patient records into a common data space with universal naming and scaling scheme. Then, corrective processes were implemented to resolve transcription issues and outlier detection based on histographic analyses and deviation from mean values. All issues identified were corrected programmatically if possible (e.g. adjust dates to ‘dd/mm/yyyy’ format), or upon requesting manual check from clinical data managers.

A. Baseline feature extraction

The most commonly reported baseline parameters are then extracted from the harmonized dataset to be used as predictive factors to assess the risk for subsequent LVEF decline in the study population. These include various features from the clinical evaluation of each patient, along with common comorbidities, clinical measures from the annotation reports of echocardiograms (echo scans) and blood reports from relevant results of prescribed lab exams. The complete list of parameters and clinical measures is presented in Table II.

TABLE III. PATIENT DISTRIBUTION PER CLASS FOR EACH FOLLOW-UP.

Follow-up from Baseline	No. of patient		
	LVEF decline (Class 1)	No LVEF decline (Class 0)	Total
Month 3	27 (7.6%)	326 (92.4%)	353
Month 6	39 (11.1%)	313 (88.9%)	352
Month 9	44 (15.5%)	239 (84.5%)	283
Month 12	48 (15.1%)	269 (84.9%)	317

B. LVEF predictive analysis

The evaluation of the risk for LVEF decline is assessed in four different follow-up intervals after baseline evaluation and initiation of chemotherapy, namely at 3, 6, 9 and 12 months. Due to the different patient follow-up protocol that was followed in each clinical center, the number of available visits per time point is not consistent. The LVEF values were used to define whether a clinically important decline was noted in a given patient or not, in order to assign patient in their respective classes (i.e. ‘LVEF decline’ vs ‘No LVEF decline’, Table III). Following guidance from the team of clinical experts and according to relative guidelines, the threshold for considering a decrease of LVEF as indicative of cardiac damage is defined as 10% (i.e. a reduction in absolute percentage points and not relative to baseline LVEF value), as follows:

$$SA_{M_n} \begin{cases} LVEF_{M_0} - LVEF_{M_n} \geq 10\%, & \text{'LVEF Decline'} \\ \text{else,} & \text{'No Decline'} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where SA_{M_n} is the sample annotation per follow-up interval, n is the month of follow-up with $n \in [3, 6, 9, 12]$.

C. Feature selection – Classification

Initially features with no variance in their samples were removed (e.g. all samples listed as ‘Female’ in ‘Gender’, ‘No’ in ‘Smoking status’, etc.). This is primarily applicable to categorical features. Then, baseline features are filtered to check for presence of missing values, removing features lacking more than 30% of their samples. High percentage of missing values in medical records is very common and it can severely limit the applicability and performance of machine learning algorithms. The final feature selection step consists of a recursive feature selection process in repetitive evaluation runs during training, starting from a single feature and adding additional features, by selecting those which reduced training loss the most. This task is performed in combination with the binary classifier to distinguish patients either to the declined LVEF value group (i.e. Class 1) or to the no decline group (i.e. Class 0), according to their actual annotation following (1). The Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Classification Tree from the Scikit-learn library [10] is selected for this task, as it offers native support for handling datasets with missing values.

D. Evaluation methodology

As it was noted in previous studies [6-8] and presented in Table III above, the proportion of breast cancer patients developing cardiac dysfunction within the first 12 months after receiving cancer treatment was relatively small. Hence, a high data samples imbalance was evident between the two classes in all follow-up intervals, which could severely impact classification performance. To address this issue without excluding any data points, the patients in the no LVEF decline

group (Class 0) were split into smaller subgroups with size proportional to the LVEF decline group (Class 1). Splits were performed randomly and each patient could be assigned only to one subgroup. Independent evaluation experiments were performed across the different subgroups of the majority class per follow-up interval to assess classification performance.

The proposed LVEF decline prediction algorithm was then evaluated using a stratified train-validate-test data split approach. Available samples per follow-up interval were shuffled and split into 30% testing, 60% training and 10% validation sets with an equal samples distribution. The feature selection steps were split-nested and evaluated with the validation set, in order to prevent information leaking from the testing dataset during the training phase. Critical hyper parameters of the classifier were also tested for better classification performance during training (i.e. learning rate=[0.01-0.5], min leaf size=[1-15]).

III. RESULTS

The evaluation results for the prediction of LVEF decline at the 4 follow-up time intervals using only baseline evaluation features are reported in Table IV, including the recall, precision, F1-score and total classification accuracy performance metrics per follow-up. The reported values were estimated by averaging their respective values obtained per individual subgroup evaluation experiment. The classification performance in all evaluation intervals was similar with F1-scores ranging from 68.73% to 74.06%. By re-balancing the two classes, stability in recall and precision could be retained with an average of 73.45% and 71.08%, respectively. The most commonly selected features are also presented in Table IV, according to their prevalence in the different evaluation experiments (i.e. the more a feature was selected the higher it ranked). From a total of 55 baseline features (Table I), 26 were

TABLE IV. EVALUATION RESULTS FOR THE PREDICTION OF A 10% OR GREATER LVEF DECLINE AT BASELINE. FACTORS ARE RANKED ACCORDING TO THEIR CONTRIBUTION IN ALL EVALUATION EXPERIMENTS.

Classification performance					
	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	F1-score	
Month 3	75.00%	67.84%	66.67%	70.33%	
Month 6	70.83%	68.29%	68.75%	68.73%	
Month 9	72.95%	73.52%	70.71%	72.80%	
Month 12	75.00%	74.65%	73.55%	74.06%	
Average:	73.45%	71.08%	69.92%	71.48%	
Baseline predictive factors relevance					
Feature	Month 3	Month 6	Month 9	Month 12	Average
Diabetes	83.33%	100%	80.00%	100%	90.83%
LVEF	75.00%	100%	100%	80.00%	88.75%
Hyperlipidemia	83.33%	100%	100%	40.00%	80.83%
Arrhythmia	58.33%	62.50%	80.00%	100%	75.21%
Hypertension	66.67%	75.00%	60%	40.00%	60.42%
CAD	25.00%	75.00%	40.00%	100%	60.00%
Other Tumour	33.33%	37.50%	80.00%	80%	57.71%
CKD	25.00%	100%	60.00%	40.00%	56.25%
Cardiomyopathy	16.67%	12.50%	80.00%	80.00%	47.29%
Age at therapy	41.67%	87.50%	20.00%	20.00%	42.29%
BSA	33.33%	12.50%	80.00%	0%	31.46%

LVEF=Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction, CAD= Coronary Artery Disease, CKD=Chronic Kidney Disease, BSA=Body Surface Area.

selected at least once. The highest ranked features in terms of selection prevalence per evaluation split are also included in Table IV (i.e. most relevant predictive factors).

IV. DISCUSSION

The decline in LVEF is a major indicator that cardiac damage has already occurred in patients receiving anti-cancer treatment, making early risk assessment, even at baseline, a critical task. The proposed methodology is the first to accomplish this using machine learning, showcasing good prediction performance in a very challenging task. Although direct comparisons with previous studies from the literature are not possible since only statistical methods have been used, the evaluation results for this preliminary analysis demonstrate the feasibility of applying AI techniques with an average accuracy and F1-score of 69.92% and 71.48%, respectively. In addition, classification performance is found to be consistent in all follow-up intervals with only small variations of less than 5% being noted across all evaluation metrics.

Regarding the time interval of the LVEF decline prediction, the results from the 4 follow-up time points that were evaluated in this work indicate that prediction accuracy was constantly improving with longer horizon windows, starting from an accuracy of 66.67% for Month 3 after baseline, and reaching 73.55% at Month 12. Although consistent, this increase could be also partially explained by the increasing number of patients whose LVEF declined by 10% or more moving forward in the treatment timeline (Table III). Cardiotoxicity manifests differently depending on the treatment plan. In the case of anthracycline treatment, cardiotoxicity can be acute and symptoms can be apparent within days after first dose, while Trastuzumab can induce impairment in cardiac function without apparent symptoms at the early phases. Using the proposed methodology, it is possible to identify a cardiotoxicity risk at multiple time points in line with official recommendations and guidelines [11].

When assessing the selected features in Table IV, as expected, the majority of the baseline factors identified are related to cardiac dysfunction. As reported in previous studies [7-9], baseline LVEF values were again found to be useful for prediction, but interestingly enough, it was the presence of Diabetes that topped the ranking chart, something that has not been reported before. A history of hyperlipidemia, arrhythmia, hypertension, chronic artery disease or cardiomyopathy were also strong determinants of an early decline in LVEF measurements in accordance to similar previous findings [9]. Older age was also found again a useful predictive factor, but it was body surface area rather than body mass index that ranked higher. Finally, regarding chronic kidney disease, none of the patients in the decline group had a positive diagnosis making it an exclusive risk factor.

Biomarkers such as troponin and NT-proBNP have been proposed as a good indicators of early cardiac toxicity, before heart failure symptoms onset and an evident LVEF drop [12]. These biomarkers were not considered as inputs to the model in this study, since only a small number of patients had such measures reported at baseline, and the <30% of missing values feature selection condition would not have been met. However, these markers will be integrated in the features list during the prospective phase of the CARDIOCARE project.

One of the greatest assets of the proposed methodology is that it was designed and developed to allow for early risk assessment in all subgroups of breast cancer patients, without focusing on a specific diagnosis or treatment route, which was commonly in previous studies in the literature [6-8]. Combined with an evaluation process using a retrospectively collected large multi-center dataset from 5 clinical centers, where variations in treatment protocols and patient management are exhibited, this is a solid indicator that real-life clinical practice conditions are met, avoiding the inherent bias that is introduced when training machine learning algorithms with limited data collection diversity.

V. CONCLUSION

This study consists the first step towards the development of a robust AI-based early risk management tool, enabling more accurate prediction at multiple time intervals. The preliminary evaluation of the proposed methodology needs to be validated with higher number of samples per follow-up and considering between-centers cross-validation approaches. Then, on the technical side, the integration of explainability models to allow for better inference of each baseline factor will enable more personalized risk assessments. These are all tasks that we plan to explore as future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Reddy, C. Shenoy, A. H. Blaes, "Cardio-oncology in the older adult," *Journal of Geriatric Oncology*, vol. 8:(4), pp 308-314, 2017.
- [2] X. Q. Yu, "Socioeconomic disparities in breast cancer survival: relation to stage at diagnosis, treatment and race," *BMC Cancer*, vol. 9, 2009.
- [3] D. Cardinale, A. Colombo, G. Bacchiani, I. Tedeschi, *et al.*, "Early detection of anthracycline cardiotoxicity and improvement with heart failure therapy," *Circulation*, vol. 131:(22), pp. 1981-1988, 2015.
- [4] D. Cardinale, G. Biasillo, C. M. Cipolla, "Curing Cancer, Saving the Heart: A Challenge That Cardiology Should Not Miss," *Current Cardiology Reports*, vol. 18:(51), 2016.
- [5] P. Thavendiranathan, F. Poulin, K. D. Lim, *et al.*, "Use of Myocardial Strain Imaging by Echocardiography for the Early Detection of Cardiotoxicity in Patients During and After Cancer Chemotherapy: A Systematic Review," *J Am Coll Cardiol*, 63:(25), pp. 2751-68, 2014.
- [6] A. Barac, "Improving prediction of cardiovascular complications of cancer therapy: what does the future hold?," *Future Cardiology*, vol. 11:(4), pp. 383-387, 2015.
- [7] E. K. Kim, J. Cho, J.-Y. Kim, *et al.*, "Early Decline in Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction Can Predict Trastuzumab-Related Cardiotoxicity in Patients with Breast Cancer: A Study Using 13 Years of Registry Data," *Cancer Res Treat*, vol. 51:(2), pp. 727-736, 2019.
- [8] J. N. Upshaw, R. Ruthazer, K. D. Miller, *et al.*, "Personalized Decision Making in Early Stage Breast Cancer: Applying Clinical Prediction Models for Anthracycline Cardiotoxicity and Breast Cancer Mortality Demonstrates Substantial Heterogeneity of Benefit-Harm Trade-off," *Clinical Breast Cancer*, vol. 19:(4), pp 259-267. 2019.
- [9] X. Liu, L. Tao, M. Wang, *et al.*, "ABSDELL Model: Development and Internal Validation of a Risk Prediction Model of LVEF Decline in Breast Cancer Patients Treated With Trastuzumab," *Clinical Breast Cancer*, vol. 23:(1), pp. 23-31, 2023.
- [10] F. Pedregosa, V. Gaël, A. Gramfort, *et al.*, "Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python," *J Mach Learn.*, vol. 12, pp. 2825-30, 2011.
- [11] S. H. Armenian, C. Lacchetti, A. Barac, *et al.*, "Prevention and Monitoring of Cardiac Dysfunction in Survivors of Adult Cancers: American Society of Clinical Oncology Clinical Practice Guideline," *J Clin Oncol*, vol. 35(8), pp. 893-911, 2017.
- [12] B. G. Demissei, R. A. Hubbard, L. Zhang, A. M. Smith, *et al.*, "Changes in Cardiovascular Biomarkers With Breast Cancer Therapy and Associations With Cardiac Dysfunction," *J Am Heart Assoc*, vol. 21;9(2):e014708, 2020.